

SHOCK PROPAGATION BEHAVIOR OF CFRP LATTICE STRUCTURES

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ABSTRACT

Anisogrid lattice structure, consisting of helical and hoop ribs intersecting each other in a regular pattern, is considered to be a superior candidate as the lightweight aerospace structure such as payload attachment adapter and inter-stage structure of launch vehicles. It is also expected that lattice structure has high wave attenuation and vibration damping properties owing to the nodal structure, which additionally motivates us to apply the lattice structure to the launch vehicle structures to reduce the high-level shock loads during the launch and the separation of the spacecraft. In this study, composite lattice structure fabricated by low-cost process is focused on, and its shock propagation behavior is experimentally evaluated. Transient responses of CFRP lattice structure by the impact are measured using accelerometers. The superior wave attenuation property of the composite lattice structures is demonstrated in comparison to several other structures reported in the previous references. Moreover, a simplified analytical method for the prediction of the shock responses of lattice structures is presented in this paper. The shock attenuation characteristics of CFRP lattice structure are explained by the analytical predictions.

1 INTRODUCTION

CFRP anisogrid lattice structure consists of helical and hoop ribs intersecting each other in a regular pattern (An example is shown in Fig. 1 and Fig. 2). Generally, CFRP lattice structure is produced in the manner that continuous carbon fibers align to each rib direction. This structure has an advantage over the conventional skin based structures in weight efficiency and fabrication cost [1,2]. The conventional skin based structure is made of numerous components such as stringers and frames, which results in a huge number of assembly processes and excessive fabrication cost. The lattice structure, on the other hand, can be produced by relatively low cost fabrication method, e.g. filament winding and fiber placement. Because of its high structural efficiency and applicability of low-cost processing methods, CFRP lattice structure is considered to be a superior candidate as the light-weight aerospace structure such as payload attachment adapter and inter-stage structure of launch vehicles [1-3]. Recently, active studies have been reported all over the world on the manufacturability, mechanical properties, and buckling behavior of CFRP lattice structure [1-6].

Spacecraft structures and payloads are subjected to high-level loads by the pyrotechnics, which are generally used in the separation stage of spacecraft and the deployment of payloads owing to high reliability. Pyroshocks induce transient elastic waves with high amplitudes and high frequencies traveling in the spacecraft structure and the payloads. Therefore, it is necessary to evaluate the pyroshock dynamic loads and reduce the pyroshock environment of spacecraft structures [7-9]. NASA reported numerous experimental data and empirical equations to estimate shock attenuation of various structures (e.g. truss structure, honeycomb structure, complex airframe structure) [8,9].

Lattice structure is expected to have high wave attenuation and vibration damping properties owing to the nodal structure, which additionally motivates us to apply the lattice structure to the launch

vehicle structures. Shock attenuation behaviour of CFRP lattice structures should be evaluated in relation to the applicability of lattice structure to spacecraft structures.

The present study reports experimental investigations of shock propagation behaviour of CFRP lattice structure which is expected to be applied to spacecraft structure. Impulse shock is induced to lattice structures by impact hammer, and transient accelerations are measured at several distances from the impact location. Comparison of measured shock attenuation behaviour with empirical data in previous references is presented. Finally, a simplified analysis on shock attenuation of lattice structure is performed based on elastic wave theory, accompanied by discussions on shock attenuation mechanisms of CFRP lattice structures.

2 EXPERIMENT ON SHOCK ATTENUATION

2.1 Specimens

Our previous study [3] demonstrated the manufacturability of CFRP lattice cylinder (Fig. 1), which was used for measurement of shock attenuation. This cylinder has the diameter of 2500mm, height of 2000mm, number of helical ribs of 71, and number of hoop ribs of 15. Additionally, two specimens (plate-like structures) were cut from the cylinder as shown in Fig. 1; one has five units in width and the other has one unit in width. This CFRP lattice structure has skin-less grids, which are the main structural components to carry the loads, and exhibits anisotropic. The helical rib angle of this CFRP lattice structure is different from 30° . This lattice structure was fabricated using continuous carbon fibers and epoxy resin by the semi-automated wet winding process [3]. Geometry of this lattice is summarized in Fig. 2.

2.2 Experimental method

Impulse load was applied to specimens using the impact hammer (GK-3100, Ono Sokki) and transient responses were measured by the acceleration sensors (353B15, PCB) mounted on the lattice specimens, as shown in Fig. 3. A stiff metal tip was mounted to the impact hammer to produce impulse load with high frequency components. Specimens were clamped at the bottom side, and accelerations in the in-plane transverse direction of helical ribs (corresponding to flexural wave in helical ribs) were measured. Acceleration sensors were mounted at x_i on two helical ribs (symmetrically associated with the impact point), and the average data were recorded as a function of distance from the impact location (x_0). Sampling frequency and duration were set as 1 MHz and 2500 μsec , respectively, for the measurement to eliminate the resonance effect of overall structures.

Figure 1: CFRP lattice structures.

Figure 2: Lattice pattern used in the specimens.

Figure 3: Impacted and measured points of impact tests.

2.3 Data analysis

Measured time histories were analyzed based on shock spectrum response (SRS) and frequency response function (FRF) in the present study. SRS is widely used as the indicator of shock environment in the space industry. SRS can be calculated by acceleration output of single-degree-of-freedom (SDOF) subjected to base excitation with measure acceleration time history, and represents the peak accelerations as a function of natural frequency of SDOF. This study utilized $Q=10$ (damping value of SDOF) and the natural frequency range up to 5 kHz to make a comparison with available data in literature [9]. FRF expresses the relationship between the input (impact load) and the output (accelerations) in frequency domain, which can be evaluated from the time history using the fast Fourier transformation (FFT).

To characterize the shock attenuation, peaks of SRSs, $SRS_p(x_i)$, and FRFs, $G(x_i, \omega)$, are normalized by those at the impact point, $SRS_p(x_0)$ and $G(x_0, \omega)$ (data of the acceleration sensor most nearby from the impact point), respectively, and the transmittance is defined as follows.

$$\alpha_{SRS}(x_i) = \frac{SRS_p(x_i)}{SRS_p(x_0)} \quad (1)$$

$$\alpha_{FRF}(x_i, \omega) = \frac{G(x_i, \omega)}{G(x_0, \omega)} \quad (2)$$

The transmittance can be evaluated as a function of distance from the impact location, which represents the shock attenuation behavior; lower transmittance denotes higher shock attenuation. More than 20 measurements were performed for each location, and the average data were utilized for the data analysis.

3 EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Time history and the corresponding Fourier spectrum of impact force are presented in Fig. 4, which indicates that uniform force components were input up to high frequencies ($\sim 5\text{kHz}$). Examples of the measured accelerations were shown in Fig. 5 at measurement points of $i = 0, 2$, and 4 of the cylindrical specimen with the corresponding SRSs. Fig. 5 indicates the shock attenuation as the distance from the impact point increases, and specifically, shock attenuation during the first few units is significant. In the SRS plots, the positive inclinations in the double logarithmic chart is observed, however, the inclination becomes flat at a specific natural frequency. This is called as knee frequency in the SRS plot, and expresses the resonance of the structure[8]. Knee frequencies can be clearly found in the SRS plots at x_2 and x_4 in Fig. 5. In the “near-field” region from the impact point, elastic wave propagation dominates the shock behavior and SRS plot generally exhibits linear increase in frequency. In contrast, both wave propagation and structural resonance dominate the shock behavior in the “mid-field” region (i.e. when the distance from the impact point increases), resulting in appearance of knee frequency in SRS plot [8]. In the present measurement, measurement duration is limited to remove the overall structural resonance effect, however, local structural resonance (see the representative unit of lattice structure) may influence the shock behavior. Therefore, the SRS plot at x_0 exhibits “near-field” characteristic, while “mid-field” characteristic is observed in SRS plots at x_2 and x_4 .

SRS peak transmittance (see eq.(1)) as a function of the distance from the impact point is summarized in Fig. 6. SRS peaks are presented as red circles in SRS plots in Fig. 5. As a comparison, empirical data denoted as “Honeycomb” and “Complex airframe” in Ref [9] are also included in Fig. 6. Honeycomb structure exhibits low shock attenuation, while complex airframe structures show highest attenuation in Ref. [9]. It is demonstrated that CFRP lattice structure exhibited excellent shock attenuation compared to traditional structures. It should be noted that cylindrical lattice structure exhibits higher attenuation than plate-like structures owing to the in-plane spreading of elastic waves.

Figure 4: Time history of impact input (left) and the corresponding spectrum (right)

Figure 5: Measured time history data and calculated SRSs at measurement point 0, 2 and 4.

Figure 6: Transmittances of SRS peak values of composite lattice structures.

FRFs corresponding to the time history in Fig. 5 (i.e. at x_0 , x_2 and x_4 in the cylindrical lattice) are presented in Fig. 7. FRF transmittance as a function of the distance from the impact point is also summarized in the right figure of Fig. 7. It is also observed that magnitude of FRFs decreases as the distance from the impact point increases. FRF transmittance is plotted in the right figure of Fig. 7 as a function of the distance. FRF transmittance decreases to lower than 20% at the third unit position from the impact point for all the frequencies. Specifically, significant attenuation is recognized at the first unit position, which is also observed in SRS peak transmittance in Fig 6. Shock attenuation in CFRP lattice structures exhibits power-law behavior associated with the distance, while distance/expansion attenuation in structures generally exhibits exponential law behavior.

Figure 7: Calculated FRFs at measurement point 0, 2 and 4 and transmittance of FRFs.

4 ANALYSIS OF SHOCK RESPONSE OF LATTICE STRUCTURE

4.1 Modelling of shock attenuation

It was confirmed that CFRP lattice structures exhibited higher shock attenuation than the conventional structures as shown in Fig. 6. The following three mechanisms can be considered for the shock attenuation of CFRP lattice structures (see Fig. 8);

1) Geometry of junctions,

Lattice structures have many nodes, and elastic waves are reflected and bifurcated at the junctions, resulting in shock attenuation.

2) Discontinuity of material properties at junctions

Number of layers are double at junctions, meaning that material properties (density and elastic modulus) are discontinuous at each junction. This discontinuity induces reflection of the elastic waves.

3) Distance attenuation.

Elastic waves generally decay during travelling owing to the damping effect of materials. This mechanism is not unique for lattice structures.

For the prediction of shock response of structures, transient analysis based on finite element method (FEM), spectrum element method (SEM), and statistical energy analysis (SEA) can be utilized [10]. SEM enables us to estimate simply the shock response in frequency domain, which is considered to be useful for the initial estimation or design. In the present study, a simplified analysis based on SEM is performed using beam models.

Each rib is modelled by a beam and shock attenuation is predicted for three mechanism. For the mechanism 1), the beams are connected at the junctions and elastic wave reflection/transmission/bifurcation is analysed using elastics wave theory [11,12]. Mechanism 2) can be also analysed using the same method (combination of beams and use of elastic wave analysis). For the distance attenuation, mechanism 3), the following equation is utilized for transmittance of longitudinal and bending waves [12].

$$T(x) = \exp(-k\eta x/2) \text{ (for longitudinal)}, T(x) = \exp(-k\eta x/4) \text{ (for flexural)} \quad (3)$$

where k is wave number, and η is the structural damping factor (0.01 is used in this study in reference to [13]).

Figure 8: Shock attenuation mechanisms of lattice structure.

4.2 Prediction of shock attenuation

Shock response at the first unit position from the impact point, which is considered to be near-field response and exhibited significant attenuation, is predicted using the above-mentioned analytical method. A representative unit structure of CFRP lattice structures is considered as shown in Fig. 9, and incident bending waves are traveling from the two helical ribs symmetrically. The transmittance of bending waves (v_{out}/v_{in}) are calculated for three attenuation mechanisms independently when unit longitudinal and bending wave is excited from the hoop rib, which is presented in Fig. 10. It can be observed that transmittance is low for the mechanism 1) (geometry of junctions) compared to other two mechanism. This means that the main shock attenuation results from the reflection/bifurcation effects at the junctions, contributing to high damping of lattice structures.

Figure 9: Transmission through one unit

Figure 10: Comparison of FRF transmittance between three shock attenuation mechanisms.

Shock responses at the first unit position from the impact point are predicted by multiplying the transmittance of three mechanisms. In the experiment, bending waves were measured using accelerometers. To compare the experimental results and the predictions, bending wave transmittance is presented in Fig. 11 in comparison with experimental FRF transmittance. The prediction indicates high shock attenuation (10-40% transmittance) at the location of the first unit position, which shows qualitatively good correlation with experimental results.

Figure 11: Comparison of FRF transmittance (1 unit) between numerical analysis and experimental results

5 CONCLUSIONS

This paper reported experimental investigations of shock propagation behaviour of CFRP lattice structure, which is expected to be applied to spacecraft structure. Shock attenuation properties of lattice structures were compared with data in the previous reports, and it was demonstrated that CFRP lattice structures exhibited higher shock attenuation than conventional structures. Simplified analysis based on the elastic wave theory in the frequency domain suggested that the geometry effect at the junctions contributes to significant damping in the lattice structures. The prediction also revealed good agreement with the experimental shock attenuation.

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